

Full 3D surface photolithography exposure system with direct laser writing and /or digital micro-mirror matrix stepping

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Introduction

Existing technology for photolithography exposure can use direct laser writing or (digital) micro-mirror matrix stepping UV light sources. We suggest a new system architecture and use these existing UV light sources and combine them with multiple axis motion system as known from CNC machine tools. This combination allows photolithography exposure to create structures in photoresist on any positive shaped 3D surface topology.

Application

Photolithography Structuring

Image: Section view of a 3D structured part (black) with photoresist layer (red) which demonstrates the photolithography process capability.

- on any positive shape 3D surface
- for etching or lift-off process
- on individual parts or on substrates / wafers

Fields of use, markets

MEMS, watchmaking, microfluidic, electrical interconnections, optics, etc.

Features

- Resolution: 2µm
- Substrate / wafer/ part size: up to diameter 200mm
- Precision: 1µm
- Light source wavelength: 365nm or 405nm
- Configuration: Direct laser writing or Digital Mirror Matrix - Stepper
- Maskless Photolithography

System Description

5 axis (or multiple axis) CNC machine motion system with high speed and high precision direct linear and rotary server motors for full 3D motion of the part.

Single or matrix tip-tilt mirror for maskless ultra fast laser patterning.

LED or laser light source with 365nm or 405nm wavelength for photoresist exposure. With use of optical fiber coupling various light sources can easily be integrated into the motion system.

Alignment microscope is integrated.

Control system with GUI graphical user interface. A software solution for mask pattern generation.